

The 'Abbāsids

also known as “Abbasid Caliphate”, “'Abbāsīd Caliphate”

By Sara Ann Knutson, University of British Columbia

Entry tags: Sufi, Shi'a Islam, Manichaeism, Zoroastrianism, Buddhist Traditions, Persian Religions, Sāsānian Religion, Islamic Traditions, Shiite/Shi'a, Sufism, Sunni, Religious Group, Christian

The 'Abbāsids, as defined here, refers to the rulers (caliphs) and ruling elites of the 'Abbāsīd Caliphate (750-1258 CE), as well as the governed people who also comprised this empire and influenced the political, social, cultural, economic developments during this period. Collectively, the 'Abbāsids created what has since become known as the “Golden Age” of Islam. Following the Mongol siege of Baghdad and the end of the 'Abbāsīd Caliphate of Baghdad in 1258 CE, Mamluk rulers re-established the 'Abbāsīd Caliphate in Cairo, from 1261 to 1517 CE. The 'Abbāsīd Caliphate of Cairo is not covered in this entry.

Date Range: 750 CE - 1258 CE

Region: 'Abbāsīd Caliphate

Region tags: Asia, Caucasus, Central Asia, Middle East, Africa, Northern Africa, Arabian Gulf, Levant, Egypt, Iran, Armenia, Iraq, al-Andalus, Southwest Asia, Arabian Peninsula, North Africa, Iberia, Persianate World, Kufa, Basra, Baghdad

Map of the 'Abbāsīd Caliphate at its largest extent, ca. 850 CE. Map includes approximate areas under the caliph's control, not autonomous dynasties.

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Zaman, Muhammad Qasim. Religion and politics under the early 'Abbāsīds: the emergence of the proto-Sunnī elite. Leiden: Brill, 1997.
- Source 2: Young, Michael J.L., John Derek Latham, and Robert Bertram Serjeant, Eds. Religion, Learning, and Science in the Abbasid Period, Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1990.
- Source 3: Al-Khatib al-Baghdadi (d. 463 AH/1071 CE), Tarikh Baghdad (History of Baghdad), 14 vols., Cairo: Maktabat al-Khanji, 1931.

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://smarthistory.org/quran-arabic-scripts/>
- Source 1 Description: Online article by Dr. Marika Sardar that introduces the history and development of Arabic scripts over the course of the 'Abbāsīd period. Contains images of examples of Arabic scripts in

'Abbāsīd-era Qur'ans.

– Source 2 URL: <https://islamicart.museumwnf.org/dynasties/dynasty/3/en>

– Source 2 Description: Online resource that introduces 'Abbāsīd-era art, with relevant links to museum-based materials from the 'Abbāsīd period, examples of 'Abbāsīd architecture, detailed timeline, and curated examples of art. Available in English, Spanish, French, and Arabic.

– Source 3 URL: <https://abbasidhistorypodcast.libsyn.com/-ep039-dr-ramon-harvey-on-ab-manr-al-mtur-d944ce-life-works-and-legacy-of-the-seminal-sunni-theologian>

– Source 3 Description: Abbasid history podcast, episode 39, featuring Dr. Ramon Harvey. The episode discusses the life, work, and legacy of the 'Abbāsīd-era Sunni theologian Abū Manṣūr al-Māturīdī (d.944 CE).

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

– Source 1 URL: <https://shamela.ws/book/736>

– Source 1 Description: Al-Khatib al-Baghdadi (d. AH 463 /1071 CE), *Tarikh Baghdad* (History of Baghdad). Beirut: Dar al-Gharb al-Islami. [In Arabic]. A classical Islamic biographical dictionary written by 'Abbāsīd-era historian Al-Khatib al-Baghdadi. The encyclopedic text contains over 7,831 biographies of intellectuals and elites, including hadith scholars. The text also contains over 4000 hadith, establishing Al-Khatib as an important source for hadith studies.

– Source 2 URL: <https://menadoc.bibliothek.uni-halle.de/publicdomain/content/titleinfo/739444>

– Source 2 Description: Abu Hasan al-Ash'ari (d. AH 324 (935/936), *Maqalat al-Islamiyyin wa Ikhtilfa al-Musallin* (The Discourses of the Proponents of Islam and the Differences Among the Worshippers), edited by Hellmut Ritter. Beirut/ Berlin, 2005. [In Arabic]. An encyclopedia of Islamic sects and discussion of Islamic theology written by 'Abbāsīd-era scholar Abu Hasan al-Ash'ari.

– Source 3 URL:

https://www.kalamullah.com/Books/The%20History%20Of%20Tabari/Tabari_Volume_30.pdf

– Source 3 Description: Muhammad ibn Jarir al-Tabari (d. AH 310/ 923 CE), *Tarikh al-rusul wa-l-mulūk* (The History of the Prophets and Kings). The link provides volume 30 from the multi-volume English translation: *The History of al-Tabari, Vol. 30: The 'Abbasid Caliphate in Equilibrium: The Caliphates of Musa al-Hadi and Harun al-Rashid A.D. 785-809/A.H. 169-193.* trans. C.E. Bosworth. New York: State University of New York Press, 1989. [In English]. A major 'Abbāsīd-era historical and religious chronicle that begins with the time of creation and describes Islamic history up to the year 915 CE. This particular volume (no. 30 from the Bosworth translations) covers the reigns of caliphs Al-Hadi and Al-Rashid.

General Variables

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

Are they written:

– Yes

↳ Are they oral:

– Yes

↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

– Yes

↳ Revealed by a high god:

– Yes

Notes: As Muslims, the 'Abbāsids believed the Qur'ān to be revealed by God to Muḥammad (sometimes through the mediation of the archangel Gabriel/Jibrīl) and, therefore, considered the Qur'ān to be the holiest and most authoritative religious text. Various theologians and theological movements during the 'Abbāsīd era disagreed on the nature of the Qur'ān (e.g., a created vs. uncreated text, something to be distinguished from divine essence or not). Ninth-century 'Abbāsīd caliph al-Ma'mūn (r. 813–833) gave official sanction to the Mu'tazilī position, namely the belief that the Qur'ān was created. The divine essence, according to the Mu'tazilah, is beyond human comprehension, whereas the Qur'ān, the divine word, is accessible to human reason.

Reference: Sonn, Tamara. "Tawḥīd". In *The Oxford Encyclopedia of the Islamic World*. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2009.

↳ Revealed by other supernatural being:

– Yes

Notes: (See explanation above)

↳ Inspired by high god:

– Yes

↳ Originated from divine or semi-divine human beings:

– No

↳ Are the scriptures alterable:

– No

↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting the scriptures:

– Yes

Notes: During the 'Abbāsīd Caliphate, various theological movements emerged and flourished, such as the Mu'tazila school.

Reference: Zaman, Muhammad Qasim. *Religion and Politics Under the Early 'abbāsids: The Emergence of the Proto-sunnī Elite*. Leiden: Brill, 1997.

↳ Can interpretation also take place outside these institutions:

– Yes

– No

Notes: Some 'Abbāsīd caliphs were more tolerant than others regarding theological interpretation. For instance, the "minha" refers to a period (833–851 CE) that began during Al-Ma'mun's reign in which religious scholars were punished, imprisoned, or killed unless they conformed to Mu'tazila doctrine. The caliph Al-Mutawakkil reversed this policy in 851 CE.

Reference: Zaman, Muhammad Qasim. *Religion and Politics Under the Early 'abbāsīds: The Emergence of the Proto-sunnī Elite*. Leiden: Brill, 1997.

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Reference: El-Hibri, Tayeb. *The Abbasid Caliphate: A History*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2021.

↳ Is the cultural contact competitive:

– Yes

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– Yes

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– Yes

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– Yes

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– Yes

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Yes

↳ In the average settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Size of largest single religious monument, square meters:

– Square meters: 37440

Notes: The sanctuary of the Great Mosque of Samarra measures 240 meters long by 156 meters wide. The outer walls of the slightly smaller Abu Dulaf Mosque (located about 15 kilometers north of Samarra) measured 213 × 135 meters.

Reference: Waardenburg, Jacques, and Akel Ismail Kahera. "Mosque". In *The Oxford Encyclopedia of the Islamic World*. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2009.

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– Height, meters: 52

Notes: At the time of its construction, the Grand Mosque of Samarra (completed in 851 CE) was the tallest mosque in the world. The spiral minaret (al-Manārah al-Malwīyah) is 52 metres high and is the largest minaret ever erected.

Reference: Al-Amid, Tahir Muzaffar. *Abbasid Architecture of Samarra in the Reign of Both Al-mu'tasim and Al-mutawakkil* (doctoral Dissertation). Edinburgh: University of Edinburgh, 1968.

Reference: Waardenburg, Jacques, and Akel Ismail Kahera. "Mosque". In *The Oxford Encyclopedia of the Islamic World*. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2009.

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– Field doesn't know

↳ In the largest settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– I don't know

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– I don't know

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– Yes

↳ Assigned by personal choice:

– Yes

↳ Assigned by class:

– No

↳ Assigned at a specific age:

– No

↳ Assigned by gender:

– No

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes

↳ Tombs:

– Yes

Reference: Allen, Terry. "The Tombs of the 'abbāsid Caliphs in Baghdād" 46, no. 3 (October 1983).
<https://doi.org/10.1017/s0041977x00043147>.

↳ Cemeteries:

– Yes

↳ Temples:

– Yes

↳ Altars:

– No

↳ Devotional markers:

– Yes

Reference: McGregor, Richard J. A.. *Islam and the Devotional Object: Seeing Religion in Egypt and Syria*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2020.

↳ Mass gathering point [plazas, courtyard, square. Places permanently demarcated using visible objects or structures]:

– Yes

Reference: Ahsan, Muhammad Manazir. *Social Life Under the Abbasids, 170-289/786-902* (doctoral Dissertation). London: University of London, 1973.

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– I don't know

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– Yes

Notes: Proselytization is usually termed da'wah (literally "call" or "invitation") in Islamic contexts.

Reference: Bulliet, Richard W.. *Conversion to Islam in the Medieval Period*. Harvard University Press, 1979. <https://doi.org/10.4159/harvard.9780674732810>.

Reference: Brinner, William M., and Devin J. Stewart. "Conversion". In *The Oxford Encyclopedia of the Islamic World*. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2009.

Is proselytization coercive:

– No

Notes: The Qur'an states, "There is no compulsion in the religion."

Does the religion have official political support

– Yes

Is religious infrastructure paid for by the polity:

– Yes

Are the head of the polity and the head of the religion the same figure:

– Yes

Notes: Broadly speaking, the caliph was considered a political- religious successor to the prophet Muhammad. But the notion of a "head of religion" works differently in Islam than in, for instance, Christianity. That said, some Muslim chroniclers during the 'Abbāsīd Caliphate compared the position of the Pope in Christianity to that of a caliph, describing the Pope as the "caliph of the Franks" (khalifat al-firani).

Are political officials equivalent to religious officials:

– Yes

Notes: (This was often, if not exclusively, the case during the 'Abbāsīd period). That said, by the second half of the ninth century CE, some Ṣūfī groups challenged the 'Abbāsīd caliphs for subordinating religious authority to the political leadership and co-opting religious clerics to positions in their offices. "The Ṣūfī response was to protect the independence of the Muslim community from interference by the state and ruling elite in matters of religious guidance" (Johansen and Talib 2009).

Reference: Johansen, J. E. A., and Mohammad Talib. "Sufism and Politics". In *The Oxford Encyclopedia of the Islamic World*. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2009.

– No

Notes: Hadia Mubarak explains that during the 'Abbāsīd period, the expansion of the Islamic domain and the preoccupation of the caliphs with ceremonials and traditions of the Persian monarchy prevented officials from personally delivering the khuṭbah (an address that is part of a religious service). Instead, a man learned in religious matters was appointed to the position of khaṭīb.

Reference: Mubarak, Hadia. "Khuṭbah". In *The Oxford Encyclopedia of the Islamic World*. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2009.

Reference: Ibn al-Jawzī, Abū al-Faraj 'Abd al-Raḥmān ibn 'Alī, and Merlin L. Swartz (Trans.). *Kitāb Al-quṣṣās Wa-al-mudhakkirīn*. Beirut: Dār al-Mashriq, 1971.

↳ Polity legal code is roughly coterminous with religious code:

– Yes

↳ Polity provides preferential economic treatment (e.g. tax, exemption)

– Yes

Notes: During the 'Abbāsīd period (and other periods of Islamic history), "jizyah" referred to a head tax, levied on non-Muslim dhimmīs (protected monotheists). "According to the Ḥanafī jurist Abū Yūsuf (d. 808), qāḍī (chief judge) for the 'Abbāsīd caliph Hārūn al-Rashīd, jizyah was a form of tribute that exempted the person who paid it from military service. Consequently, it was not required from those incapable of fighting. Abū Yūsuf also conceived of jizyah as a graduated head tax, in which the poor paid less than the rich, and the elderly, women, children, the sick, and the penniless were exempted. For the jurist and law-school founder al-Shāfi'ī (d. 820), jizyah was a tributary and protection tax that was required of all dhimmīs, regardless of status. However, if a Muslim ruler failed his non-Muslim subjects by not providing them with adequate security, he was obliged to return the money. This was actually done for Christians by the Egyptian amīr Ṣalāḥ al-Dīn al-Ayyūbī ("Saladin," d. 1193), when he was compelled to withdraw his army from Syria" (Cornell 2009).

Reference: Cornell, Vincent J.. "Jizyah". In *The Oxford Encyclopedia of the Islamic World*. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2009.

Is iconography present:

– Yes

↳ Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

– At home

– Some public spaces

↳ Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

– Yes

↳ Humans:

– Yes

Reference: Hoffman, Eva. "Between East and West: The Wall Paintings of Samarra and the Construction of Abbasid Princely Culture". *Muqarnas* 25 (2008): 107-32.

↳ Other features of iconography:

– Yes

Notes: For example, "giriḥ" (decorative Islamic geometric patterns) is often used in Islamic architecture and objects.

Reference: Grabar, Oleg. *Early Islamic Art, 650-1100*. Routledge, 2023.

<https://doi.org/10.4324/9781003418498>.

Reference: Ettinghausen, Richard, Oleg Grabar, and Marilyn Jenkins-Madina. *Islamic Art and Architecture, 650-1250 (2nd Ed.)*. New Haven: Yale University Press, 2002.

Reference: Flood, Finbarr Barry, and Gülru Necipoğlu, eds.. *A Companion to Islamic Art and Architecture*. Edited by Finbarr Barry Flood and Gülru Necipoğlu. Wiley, 2017.

<https://doi.org/10.1002/9781119069218>.

Reference: Saba, Matthew D.. "ABBASID LUSTERWARE AND THE AESTHETICS OF 'AJAB'" 29, no. 1 (January 1, 2012). <https://doi.org/10.1163/22118993-90000187>.

Reference: Shaw, Wendy. "Journal of Art Historiography Number 6 June 2012 the Islam in Islamic Art History: Secularism and Public Discourse". *Journal of Art Historiography* 6 (2012): 1-34.

Reference: Bloom, Jonathan M., and Sheila S. Blair, eds.. *The Grove Encyclopedia of Islamic Art and Architecture*. Edited by Jonathan M. Bloom and Sheila S. Blair. Oxford University Press, 2009. <https://doi.org/10.1093/acref/9780195309911.001.0001>.

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Cook, David. "Apostasy in Islam: A Historical Perspective." *Journal of Arabic and Islamic Studies* 31 (2006): 248-288.

↳ Are apostates prosecuted or punished:

– Yes

↳ Do apostates receive corporal punishment:

– Yes

↳ Apostates are executed:

– Yes

Notes: In most cases, the punishment of apostasy by execution seems to have

been rare. Cook, David. "Apostasy in Islam: A Historical Perspective." *Journal of Arabic and Islamic Studies* 31 (2006): 248-288.

– No

– No

Nature of religious group [please select one]:

– Large official religious group with smaller religious groups also openly allowed

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Yes

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

Are leaders believed to possess supernatural powers or qualities:

– No

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

Notes: 'Abbāsīd caliphs often personally led pilgrimages to Mecca and invested in pilgrimage infrastructure. Of all the 'Abbāsīd caliphs, Harun al-Rashid is the caliph who made the most pilgrimage trips during his lifetime. Al-Rashid's wife, Zubaidah bint Ja'far, also provided support for pilgrimages, including the construction of a pilgrimage road known as Darb Zubaydah (from Kufa to Mecca).

Reference: El-Hibri, Tayeb. *The Abbasid Caliphate: A History*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2021.

Reference: Al-Rashid, Saad A.. "Darb Zubaydah in the 'abbāsīd Period: Historical and Archaeological Aspects". *Proceedings of the Seminar for Arabian Studies* 8 (1978): 33-45.

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

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Reference: El-Hibri, Tayeb. *The Abbasid Caliphate: A History*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2021.

Is the cultural contact competitive:

– Yes

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

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↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

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– Yes

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– Yes

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– Yes

↳ Assigned by personal choice:

– Yes

↳ Assigned by class:

– No

↳ Assigned at a specific age:

– No

↳ Assigned by gender:

– No

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

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Notes: Proselytization is usually termed da‘wah (literally “call” or “invitation”) in Islamic contexts.

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↳ Are the head of the polity and the head of the religion the same figure:

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Notes: Broadly speaking, the caliph was considered a political- religious successor to the prophet Muhammad. But the notion of a "head of religion" works differently in Islam than in, for instance, Christianity. That said, some Muslim chroniclers during the 'Abbāsīd Caliphate compared the position of the Pope in Christianity to that of a caliph, describing the Pope as the "caliph of the Franks" (khalifat al-firani).

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Notes: In most cases, the punishment of apostasy by execution seems to have been rare. Cook, David. "Apostasy in Islam: A Historical Perspective." *Journal of Arabic and Islamic Studies* 31 (2006): 248-288.

– No

– No

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population,

numerical):

– I don't know

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– I don't know

Nature of religious group [please select one]:

– Large official religious group with smaller religious groups also openly allowed

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

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↳ Are leaders believed to possess supernatural powers or qualities:

– No

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

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↳ Are they written:

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↳ Are they oral:

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↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

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Notes: As Muslims, the 'Abbāsids believed the Qur'ān to be revealed by God to Muḥammad (sometimes through the mediation of the archangel Gabriel/Jibrīl) and, therefore, considered the Qur'ān to be the holiest and most authoritative religious text.

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↳ Can interpretation also take place outside these institutions:

– Yes

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Reference: Zaman, Muhammad Qasim. *Religion and Politics Under the Early 'abbāsīds: The Emergence of the Proto-sunnī Elite*. Leiden: Brill, 1997.

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

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↳ Size of largest single religious monument, square meters:

– Square meters: 37440

Notes: The sanctuary of the Great Mosque of Samarra measures 240 meters long by 156 meters wide. The outer walls of the slightly smaller Abu Dulaf Mosque (located about 15 kilometers north of Samarra) measured 213 × 135 meters.

Reference: Waardenburg, Jacques, and Akel Ismail Kahera. "Mosque". In *The Oxford Encyclopedia of the Islamic World*. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2009.

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

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Notes: At the time of its construction, the Grand Mosque of Samarra (completed in 851 CE) was the tallest mosque in the world. The spiral minaret (al-Manārah al-Malwīyah) is 52 metres high and is the largest minaret ever erected.

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Reference: Waardenburg, Jacques, and Akel Ismail Kahera. "Mosque". In *The Oxford Encyclopedia of the Islamic World*. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2009.

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– Field doesn't know

↳ In the largest settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– I don't know

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes

↳ Tombs:

– Yes

Reference: Allen, Terry. "The Tombs of the 'abbāsīd Caliphs in Baghdād" 46, no. 3 (October 1983).
<https://doi.org/10.1017/s0041977x00043147>.

↳ Cemeteries:

– Yes

↳ Temples:

– Yes

↳ Altars:

– No

↳ Devotional markers:

– Yes

Reference: McGregor, Richard J. A.. *Islam and the Devotional Object: Seeing Religion in Egypt and Syria*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2020.

↳ Mass gathering point [plazas, courtyard, square. Places permanently demarcated using visible objects or structures]:

– Yes

Reference: Ahsan, Muhammad Manazir. *Social Life Under the Abbasids, 170-289/786-902* (doctoral Dissertation). London: University of London, 1973.

Is iconography present:

– Yes

↳ Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

– At home

– Some public spaces

↳ Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

– Yes

↳ Humans:

– Yes

Reference: Hoffman, Eva. "Between East and West: The Wall Paintings of Samarra and the Construction of Abbasid Princely Culture". *Muqarnas* 25 (2008): 107-32.

Other features of iconography:

– Yes

Notes: For example, "giriḥ" (decorative Islamic geometric patterns) is often used in Islamic architecture and objects.

Reference: Grabar, Oleg. *Early Islamic Art, 650-1100*. Routledge, 2023.
<https://doi.org/10.4324/9781003418498>.

Reference: Ettinghausen, Richard, Oleg Grabar, and Marilyn Jenkins-Madina. *Islamic Art and Architecture, 650-1250 (2nd Ed.)*. New Haven: Yale University Press, 2002.

Reference: Flood, Finbarr Barry, and Gülru Necipoğlu, eds.. *A Companion to Islamic Art and Architecture*. Edited by Finbarr Barry Flood and Gülru Necipoğlu. Wiley, 2017.
<https://doi.org/10.1002/9781119069218>.

Reference: Saba, Matthew D.. "ABBASID LUSTERWARE AND THE AESTHETICS OF 'AJAB" 29, no. 1 (January 1, 2012). <https://doi.org/10.1163/22118993-90000187>.

Reference: Shaw, Wendy. "Journal of Art Historiography Number 6 June 2012 the Islam in Islamic Art History: Secularism and Public Discourse". *Journal of Art Historiography* 6 (2012): 1-34.

Reference: Bloom, Jonathan M., and Sheila S. Blair, eds.. *The Grove Encyclopedia of Islamic Art and Architecture*. Edited by Jonathan M. Bloom and Sheila S. Blair. Oxford University Press, 2009. <https://doi.org/10.1093/acref/9780195309911.001.0001>.

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Yes

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

Notes: 'Abbāsīd caliphs often personally led pilgrimages to Mecca and invested in pilgrimage infrastructure. Of all the 'Abbāsīd caliphs, Harun al-Rashid is the caliph who made the most pilgrimage trips during his lifetime. Al-Rashid's wife, Zubaidah bint Ja'far, also provided support for pilgrimages, including the construction of a pilgrimage road known as Darb Zubaydah (from Kufa to Mecca).

Reference: El-Hibri, Tayeb. *The Abbasid Caliphate: A History*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2021.

Reference: Al-Rashid, Saad A.. "Darb Zubaydah in the 'abbāsīd Period: Historical and Archaeological Aspects". *Proceedings of the Seminar for Arabian Studies* 8 (1978): 33-45.

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body.

Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Yes

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body:

– Yes

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:

Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously "moral" or "ethical" norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:

– Yes

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Are messianic beliefs present:

– Yes

Reference: Yücesoy, Hayrettin. *Messianic Beliefs and Imperial Politics in Medieval Islam: The ‘abbāsīd Caliphate in the Early Ninth Century*. Columbia: The University of South Carolina Press, 2009.

Reference: Peterson, Daniel C.. “Eschatology”. In *The Oxford Encyclopedia of the Islamic World*. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2009.

Reference: Cook, David. *Studies in Muslim Apocalyptic*. Berlin: Gerlach Press, 2003.

Reference: Sachedina, Abdulaziz Abdulhussein. *Islamic Messianism: The Idea of Mahdī in Twelver Shī‘ism*. Albany: State University of New York Press, 1981.

Reference: Sachedina, Abdulaziz. “Messianism”. In *The Oxford Encyclopedia of the Islamic World*. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2009.

Is the messiah's whereabouts or time of coming known?

– No

Is the messiah's purpose known:

– Yes

Notes: The notion of the Mahdī (rightly guided one) does not appear by name in the Qur‘ān but nevertheless became an important eschatological tradition in various strands of Islam, beginning during the ‘Abbāsīd era (late seventh century). The term gradually referred to hopes for a ruler who would restore Islam to its original perfection. The Mahdī appears in both Sunnī and Shī‘ī belief, both is particularly prevalent in Shī‘ī belief. See Peterson (2009) and Sachedina (2009) for further discussion and references.

Messiah is a political figure who restores political rule:

– Yes

Notes: Various traditions about the Mahdī, beginning in the ‘Abbāsīd period, differ about the specifics regarding this figure, but Sunnī and Shī‘ī traditions generally agree that the Mahdī will rule the world briefly and will generously distribute great wealth. The Mahdī is expected to die some time before the day of resurrection, and a brief period of turmoil, uncertainty, and temptation will follow his death. See Peterson (2009) and Sachedina (2009) for further discussion and references.

Messiah is a priestly figure who restores religious traditions:

– Yes

Notes: (See above)

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

– No

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):

– No

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:

– No

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:

– Yes [specify]: The authority of the Prophet Muḥammad stems from his relationship to God.

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:

– Yes [specify]: knowledge of the unseen (al-ghayb)

↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can reward:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can punish:

– Yes

- ↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes

- ↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:
 - No

- ↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:
 - No

- ↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:
 - No

- ↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:
 - Yes [specify]: In Islam, God can and does communicate with human beings by revealing scriptures to prophets (anbiyā') and messengers (rusul).

- ↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:
 - Yes
 - ↳ In waking, everyday life:
 - Yes
 - ↳ In dreams:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Only through religious specialists:
 - No
 - ↳ Only through monarch
 - No
 - ↳ Other form of communication with living:
 - I don't know

- ↳ Previously human spirits are present:
 - I don't know

- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:
 - Yes
- ↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:
 - Yes
- ↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:
 - Yes
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:
 - Yes
- ↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:
 - Yes
- ↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:
 - Yes
- ↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:
 - Yes

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– Yes

Reference: Jokisch, Benjamin. *Islamic Imperial Law: Harun-al-rashid's Codification Project*. Berlin: Walter de Gruyter, 2007.

Reference: Sanders, Paula, and Christopher Melchert. "The Formation of the Sunni Schools of Law, 9th-10th Centuries C. E." 43, no. 1 (January 1999). <https://doi.org/10.2307/846146>.

Reference: Tsafirir, Nurit. *The History of an Islamic School of Law: The Early Spread of Hanafism*. Cambridge: Islamic Legal Studies Program, Harvard Law School, 2004.

Reference: Rabb, Intisar A.. "Law". In *The Oxford Encyclopedia of the Islamic World*. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2009.

↳ What is the nature of this distinction:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Concepts of conventional norms vs. moral norms were intensely debated during the 'Abbāsīd period. This is clearly seen, for instance, in debates among moral and political theorists regarding Islamic justice. As Ibrahim M. Abu-Rabi' explains, in the eighth century, the Mu'tazilah argued that divine justice is beyond human grasp but that human reason can best approximate divine justice through the exercise of reason and free will. They argued that through such acts, one gains unity with an inner sense of justice toward which all men are naturally directed. In the legalist position (including al-Shāfi'ī [767-820]) men choose to do justice or injustice through their adherence to the law; according to al-Ash'arī (d. 935 or 936) men could do justice but could not create its very terms. By contrast, the Shī'ī theorists of the Būyid and Fāṭimid dynasties of the tenth and eleventh centuries argued that, in the absence of an infallibly sinless imam, men may even defend themselves through taqīyah (dissimulation) against an unjust caliph. Ṣūfī theorists, such as Ibn al-'Arabī (1165-1240), instead argued that justice can be made manifest in this world not by creative acts of reason but only by engagement in ecstatic devotion.

Reference: Abu-Rabi', Ibrahim M.. "Justice". In *The Oxford Encyclopedia of the Islamic World*. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2009.

↳ Are specifically moral norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Moral norms apply to:

– All individuals (any time period)

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:

– No

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– I don't know

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– No

↳ Done by other entities or through other means [specify]

– I don't know

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Yes

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– Yes

↳ Done randomly:

– No

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural punishments in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– No

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as an inferior life form:

– No

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in an inferior realm:

– No

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural punishments in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck:

– No

↳ Punishment in this life consists of political failure:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of defeat in battle:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of crop failure or bad weather:

– I don't know

↳ Punishment in this life consists of disaster on journeys.

– I don't know

↳ Punishment in this life consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– I don't know

↳ Punishment in this life consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– I don't know

↳ Punishment in this life consists of sickness or illness:

– I don't know

↳ Punishment in this life consists of impaired reproduction:

– I don't know

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck visited on descendants:

– I don't know

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:

– No

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– No

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Yes

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness[]:

– Yes

↳ Done randomly:

– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural rewards in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

- ↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of mild sensory pleasure:
 - No
- ↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory pleasure:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of eternal happiness:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as a superior life form:
 - No
- ↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in a superior realm:
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural rewards in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of political success or power:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of success in battle:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of peace or social stability:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of healthy crops or good weather:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of success on journeys:
 - I don't know

- ↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure:
 - No
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants:
 - I don't know

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

- ↳ Cremation:
 - No
- ↳ Mummification:
 - No
- ↳ Interment:
 - Yes
- ↳ Cannibalism:
 - No
- ↳ Feeding to animals:
 - No
- ↳ Re-treatment of corpse:
 - No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

Reference: Allen, Terry. "The Tombs of the 'abbāsīd Caliphs in Baghdād" 46, no. 3 (October 1983).
<https://doi.org/10.1017/s0041977x00043147>.

↳ As cenotaphs:

– Yes

Notes: For example, the cenotaphs at Qubba al-Khulafa al-'Abbasiyin.
<https://dome.mit.edu/handle/1721.3/146720>

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

Reference: Russell, Dorothea. "A Note on the Cemetery of the Abbasid Caliphs of Cairo and the Shrine of Saiyida Nafīsa". *Ars Islamica* 6, no. 2 (1939): 168–74.

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– Yes

Is an eschatology present:

– Yes

Reference: Ja'fari, Sayyid Husayn Muhammad. *The Origins and Early Development of Shia Islam*. Lulu Press, Inc, 2014.
https://books.google.com/books/about/The_Origins_and_Early_Development_of_Shi.html?hl=&id=kztVCAAAQBAJ.

Reference: Taylor, John B.. "Some Aspects of Islamic Eschatology" 4, no. 1 (October 1968).
<https://doi.org/10.1017/s0034412500003395>.

Reference: Walker, Paul E., and Abdulaziz Abdulhussein Sachedina. "Islamic Messianism: The Idea of the Mahdi in Twelver Shi'ism" 103, no. 3 (July 1983). <https://doi.org/10.2307/602047>.

Reference: Peterson, Daniel C.. "Eschatology". In *The Oxford Encyclopedia of the Islamic World*. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2009.

↳ Eschaton in this lifetime:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Eschaton at specified time in future:

– No

↳ Eschaton at unspecified time in near future:

– Yes

↳ Eschaton at unspecified time in distant future:

– No

↳ Adherents need to perform specific tasks to bring about World's end:

– No

↳ Divine judgment event:

– Yes

↳ Restoration of the world:

– No

↳ Start of a new temporal cycle:

– No

↳ Establishment of a new political system:

– No

↳ Establishment of a new religious system:

– No

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer “no” only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Yes

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body:
– Yes

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

↳ Cremation:
– No

↳ Mummification:
– No

↳ Interment:
– Yes

↳ Cannibalism:
– No

↳ Feeding to animals:
– No

↳ Re-treatment of corpse:
– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

Reference: Allen, Terry. "The Tombs of the 'abbāsid Caliphs in Baghdād" 46, no. 3 (October 1983).

<https://doi.org/10.1017/s0041977x00043147>.

↳ As cenotaphs:

– Yes

Notes: For example, the cenotaphs at Qubba al-Khulafa al-'Abbasiyin.

<https://dome.mit.edu/handle/1721.3/146720>

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

Reference: Russell, Dorothea. "A Note on the Cemetery of the Abbasid Caliphs of Cairo and the Shrine of Saiyida Nafisa". *Ars Islamica* 6, no. 2 (1939): 168-74.

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– Yes

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

– No

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):

– No

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:

– No

- ↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:
 - Yes [specify]: The authority of the Prophet Muḥammad stems from his relationship to God.

- ↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:
 - Yes

- ↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:
 - Yes

- ↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:
 - No

- ↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:
 - No

- ↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:
 - Yes

- ↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:
 - Yes

- ↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):
 - Yes

- ↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):
 - Yes

- ↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):
 - Yes

- ↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):
 - Yes

- ↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:
 - Yes [specify]: knowledge of the unseen (al-ghayb)
- ↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god can reward:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god can punish:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:
 - No
- ↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:
 - Yes [specify]: In Islam, God can and does communicate with human beings by revealing scriptures to prophets (anbiyā') and messengers (rusul).
- ↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:
 - Yes
 - ↳ In waking, everyday life:
 - Yes

- ↳ In dreams:
 - Yes
- ↳ Only through religious specialists:
 - No
- ↳ Only through monarch
 - No
- ↳ Other form of communication with living:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Previously human spirits are present:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:
 - Yes
 - ↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:
 - Yes
 - ↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:
 - Yes
 - ↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:
 - Yes
 - ↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:
 - Yes
 - ↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:
 - I don't know

- ↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:
 - Yes

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

- ↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:
Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously “moral” or “ethical” norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:
 - Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:

– Yes

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

- ↳ Done only by high god:
 - No
- ↳ Done by many supernatural beings:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:
 - No
- ↳ Done by other entities or through other means [specify]
 - I don't know
- ↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Done to enforce group norms:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Done randomly:
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Supernatural punishments in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of mild sensory displeasure:
 - No

- ↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory displeasure:
 - Yes
- ↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as an inferior life form:
 - No
- ↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in an inferior realm:
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural punishments in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:
 - Yes
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck:
 - No
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of political failure:
 - Yes
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of defeat in battle:
 - Yes
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of crop failure or bad weather:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of disaster on journeys.
 - I don't know
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of mild sensory displeasure:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of extreme sensory displeasure:
 - I don't know

- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of sickness or illness:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of impaired reproduction:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck visited on descendants:
 - I don't know

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

- ↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Done only by high god:
 - No
 - ↳ Done by many supernatural beings:
 - Field doesn't know
 - ↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:
 - No
 - ↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Done to enforce group norms:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Done randomly:
 - No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural rewards in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of mild sensory pleasure:

– No

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory pleasure:

– Yes

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of eternal happiness:

– Yes

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as a superior life form:

– No

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in a superior realm:

– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural rewards in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of political success or power:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of success in battle:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of peace or social stability:

– Yes

- ↳ Reward in this life consists of healthy crops or good weather:
– I don't know
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of success on journeys:
– I don't know
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure:
– No
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure:
– I don't know
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health:
– I don't know
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success:
– I don't know
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants:
– I don't know

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– Yes

Reference: Yücesoy, Hayrettin. *Messianic Beliefs and Imperial Politics in Medieval Islam: The 'abbāsid Caliphate in the Early Ninth Century*. Columbia: The University of South Carolina Press, 2009.

Reference: Peterson, Daniel C.. "Eschatology". In *The Oxford Encyclopedia of the Islamic World*. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2009.

Reference: Cook, David. *Studies in Muslim Apocalyptic*. Berlin: Gerlach Press, 2003.

Reference: Sachedina, Abdulaziz Abdulhussein. *Islamic Messianism: The Idea of Mahdī in Twelver Shi'ism*. Albany: State University of New York Press, 1981.

Reference: Sachedina, Abdulaziz. "Messianism". In *The Oxford Encyclopedia of the Islamic World*. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2009.

- ↳ Is the messiah's whereabouts or time of coming known?
– No

↳ Is the messiah's purpose known:

– Yes

Notes: The notion of the Mahdī (rightly guided one) does not appear by name in the Qur'ān but nevertheless became an important eschatological tradition in various strands of Islam, beginning during the 'Abbāsīd era (late seventh century). The term gradually referred to hopes for a ruler who would restore Islam to its original perfection. The Mahdī appears in both Sunnī and Shī'ī belief, both is particularly prevalent in Shī'ī belief. See Peterson (2009) and Sachedina (2009) for further discussion and references.

↳ Messiah is a political figure who restores political rule:

– Yes

Notes: Various traditions about the Mahdī, beginning in the 'Abbāsīd period, differ about the specifics regarding this figure, but Sunnī and Shī'ī traditions generally agree that the Mahdī will rule the world briefly and will generously distribute great wealth. The Mahdī is expected to die some time before the day of resurrection, and a brief period of turmoil, uncertainty, and temptation will follow his death. See Peterson (2009) and Sachedina (2009) for further discussion and references.

↳ Messiah is a priestly figure who restores religious traditions:

– Yes

Notes: (See above)

Is an eschatology present:

– Yes

Reference: Ja'fari, Sayyid Husayn Muhammad. *The Origins and Early Development of Shia Islam*. Lulu Press, Inc, 2014.

https://books.google.com/books/about/The_Origins_and_Early_Development_of_Shi.html?hl=&id=kztVCAAAQBAJ.

Reference: Taylor, John B.. "Some Aspects of Islamic Eschatology" 4, no. 1 (October 1968). <https://doi.org/10.1017/s0034412500003395>.

Reference: Walker, Paul E., and Abdulaziz Abdulhussein Sachedina. "Islamic Messianism: The Idea of the Mahdi in Twelver Shi'ism" 103, no. 3 (July 1983). <https://doi.org/10.2307/602047>.

Reference: Peterson, Daniel C.. "Eschatology". In *The Oxford Encyclopedia of the Islamic World*. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2009.

↳ Eschaton in this lifetime:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Eschaton at specified time in future:

– No

- ↳ Eschaton at unspecified time in near future:
 - Yes
- ↳ Eschaton at unspecified time in distant future:
 - No
- ↳ Adherents need to perform specific tasks to bring about World's end:
 - No
- ↳ Divine judgment event:
 - Yes
- ↳ Restoration of the world:
 - No
- ↳ Start of a new temporal cycle:
 - No
- ↳ Establishment of a new political system:
 - No
- ↳ Establishment of a new religious system:
 - No

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– Yes

Reference: Jokisch, Benjamin. *Islamic Imperial Law: Harun-al-rashid's Codification Project*. Berlin: Walter de Gruyter, 2007.

Reference: Sanders, Paula, and Christopher Melchert. "The Formation of the Sunni Schools of Law, 9th-10th Centuries C. E." 43, no. 1 (January 1999). <https://doi.org/10.2307/846146>.

Reference: Tsafrir, Nurit. *The History of an Islamic School of Law: The Early Spread of Hanafism*. Cambridge: Islamic Legal Studies Program, Harvard Law School, 2004.

Reference: Rabb, Intisar A.. "Law". In *The Oxford Encyclopedia of the Islamic World*. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2009.

↳ What is the nature of this distinction:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Concepts of conventional norms vs. moral norms were intensely debated during the 'Abbāsīd period. This is clearly seen, for instance, in debates among moral and political theorists regarding Islamic justice. As Ibrahim M. Abu-Rabi' explains, in the eighth century, the Mu'tazilah argued that divine justice is beyond human grasp but that human reason can best approximate divine justice through the exercise of reason and free will. They argued that through such acts, one gains unity with an inner sense of justice toward which all men are naturally directed. In the legalist position (including al-Shāfi'ī [767-820]) men choose to do justice or injustice through their adherence to the law; according to al-Ash'arī (d. 935 or 936) men could do justice but could not create its very terms. By contrast, the Shī'ī theorists of the Būyid and Fāṭimid dynasties of the tenth and eleventh centuries argued that, in the absence of an infallibly sinless imam, men may even defend themselves through taqīyah (dissimulation) against an unjust caliph. Ṣūfī theorists, such as Ibn al-'Arabī (1165-1240), instead argued that justice can be made manifest in this world not by creative acts of reason but only by engagement in ecstatic devotion.

Reference: Abu-Rabi', Ibrahim M.. "Justice". In *The Oxford Encyclopedia of the Islamic World*. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2009.

↳ Are specifically moral norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Moral norms apply to:

– All individuals (any time period)

Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– Yes

↳ Monogamy (males):

– No

↳ Monogamy (females):

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– Yes

Notes: Like other Muslims, the 'Abbāsids fasted during the month of Ramaḍān and observed supererogatory fasts for spiritual benefit.

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– Yes

Notes: Male circumcision

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings

or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– I don't know

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– I don't know

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

I.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– Yes

↳ On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

– Yes

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

– Yes

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:

– Yes

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– Yes

↳ Tattoos/scarification:

– No

↳ Circumcision:

– Yes

↳ Food taboos:

– Yes

↳ Hair:

– Yes

↳ Dress:

– Yes

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– No

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– Yes

↳ Monogamy (males):

– No

↳ Monogamy (females):

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– Yes

Notes: Like other Muslims, the 'Abbāsids fasted during the month of Ramaḍān and observed supererogatory fasts for spiritual benefit.

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– Yes

Notes: Male circumcision

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– I don't know

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– I don't know

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

I.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– Yes

↳ On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

– Yes

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

– Yes

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:

– Yes

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– Yes

↳ Tattoos/scarification:

– No

↳ Circumcision:

– Yes

↳ Food taboos:

– Yes

↳ Hair:

– Yes

↳ Dress:

– Yes

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– No

Society and Institutions

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– An empire

– A state

Notes: The term "caliphate" (khilāfah) refers to a political institution which is under the leadership of an Islamic steward, the caliph. Note that some people who lived outside the ever-changing boundaries of the caliphate still considered themselves part of the umma, the Muslim community. Also note that the modern understanding of "dawlah" as a sovereign state does not fully map onto 'Abbāsīd-era understandings of the term (see Akhavi 2009 for further discussion).

Reference: Akhavi, Shahrough. "Dawlah". In *The Oxford Encyclopedia of the Islamic World*. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2009.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– Yes

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Yes

Notes: Beginning in the Umayyad dynasty and into the early 'Abbāsīd period, proto-schools of fiqh ("knowledge," with legal, theological, and spiritual implications, connected to the Qur'ān) developed, composed of regional circles of students who self-consciously followed a principal teacher who was an accomplished, scholarly authority in their vicinity. "Regional schools crystallized into formal legal schools (madhhabs) in the late ninth to mid-tenth centuries, each having developed a set of positive legal rules and a particular jurisprudential methodology. Each regional scholar had his own approach, but all agreed broadly on the sources of law" (Rabb 2009). The Bayt al-Ḥikmah (House of Wisdom) was founded

in 830 CE, during the reign of 'Abbāsīd caliph al-Ma'mūn (r. 813–833). As the leading library of its time, the Bayt al-Ḥikmah became a center of translation and included an academy for scholars; it was therefore a major center of learning in the Islamic world.

Reference: Bennison, Amira K.. *The Great Caliphs: The Golden Age of the 'abbasid Empire*. London: I.B. Tauris, 2011.

Reference: El-Hibri, Tayeb. *The Abbasid Caliphate: A History*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2021.

Reference: Rabb, Intisar A.. "Fiqh". In *The Oxford Encyclopedia of the Islamic World*. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2009.

Reference: Monastra, Yahyá, and William J. Kopycki. "Libraries". In *The Oxford Encyclopedia of the Islamic World*. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2009.

↳ Is formal education restricted to religious professionals:
– No

↳ Is such education open to both males and females:
– Yes

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Yes

Reference: Sourdel, Dominique. *Le Vizirat 'abbāsīde*. Damascus: Institut français de Damas, 1959.

Reference: Özdemir, Öznur. "Early Islamic Institutions: Administration and Taxation from the Caliphate to the Umayyads and Abbāsīds" 4, no. 3 (November 30, 2018). <https://doi.org/10.25272/ijisef.490018>.

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– Yes

Reference: Talib, M.. "Annals of the Caliphs' Kitchens: Ibn Sayyar Al-warrāq's Tenth-century Baghdadi Cookbook (english Translation with Introduction and Glossary) * by NAWAL NASRALLAH" 21, no. 2 (April 18, 2010). <https://doi.org/10.1093/jis/etq012>.

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– Yes

Reference: Bennison, Amira K.. *The Great Caliphs: The Golden Age of the 'abbasid Empire*. London: I.B. Tauris, 2011.

Reference: Özdemir, Öznur. "Early Islamic Institutions: Administration and Taxation from the Caliphate to the Umayyads and Abbāsīds" 4, no. 3 (November 30, 2018). <https://doi.org/10.25272/ijisef.490018>.

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– Yes

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– Yes

Reference: Gordon, Matthew. "The Turkish Officers of Samarra: Revenue and the Exercise of Authority" 42, no. 4 (1999). <https://doi.org/10.1163/1568520991201713>.

Reference: Gordon, Matthew S. *The Breaking of a Thousand Swords: A History of the Turkish Military of Samarra (A.H. 200-275/815-889 C.E.)*. Albany, NY: State University of New York Press, 2001.

Reference: Kennedy, Hugh. *The Armies of the Caliphs*. Routledge, 2013.
<https://doi.org/10.4324/9780203458532>.

Does the religious group in question have the power to conscript:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question maintain a full-time military corps (e.g. Swiss Guard):

– Yes

Does the religious group in question maintain a standing army:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

Reference: Zaouli, Lilia. *Medieval Cuisine of the Islamic World*. Berkeley: University of California Press, 2007.

Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

– Gathering

– Hunting (including marine animals)

– Fishing

– Pastoralism

– Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards

– Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Notes: Classical Arabic was used during the 'Abbāsid period, although the language was not limited to

usage by Muslims. That said, Arabic held (and continues to hold) a special status as the language of the Qur'an.

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– Yes

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Please characterize the forms/levels of food production [choose all that apply]:

– Gathering

– Hunting (including marine animals)

– Fishing

– Pastoralism

– Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards

– Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Yes

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the

religious group in question:

– I don't know

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– Yes

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Theoretically, all offenses were to be tried by the qāḍī, the sharī'ah judge. But Farhat J. Ziadeh argues that the qāḍī must have lost criminal jurisdiction very early in the Islamic centuries including but not limited to the fact that rulers of Islamic empires and states, like the 'Abbāsids, "could not leave matters of crime affecting state security in the hands of religious authorities who were loyal to a body of laws over which the state had no control... As a result the shurṭah (police) assumed the duty of investigating, prosecuting, and sentencing for most crimes with no distinction between one function and the other. The muḥtasib (inspector of the marketplace) punished those trade infractions and offenses against morals that were apparent and did not require testimony before a qāḍī's court. In addition, beginning in the early years of the 'Abbāsīd regime in the latter part of the eighth century, a new jurisdiction, called maẓālim (court of grievances) headed by the ruler, vizier, or governor, undertook to repress wrongdoers whom other courts could not control and generally to restrain oppression by officials. None of these jurisdictions was limited by the sharī'ah, as the qāḍī was. They applied mainly to customary law ('urf) or what political expediency (siyāsah) required; punishments were often arbitrary and severe."

Reference: Ziadeh, Farhat J.. "Criminal Law". In *The Oxford Encyclopedia of the Islamic World*. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2009.

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– Yes

Reference: Bennison, Amira K.. *The Great Caliphs: The Golden Age of the 'abbasid Empire*. London: I.B. Tauris, 2011.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– Yes

Reference: Bennison, Amira K.. *The Great Caliphs: The Golden Age of the 'abbasid Empire*. London: I.B. Tauris, 2011.

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– Yes

Reference: Ghassan Mahmoud Weshah. "THE RIGHTS OF PRISONERS IN THE ABBASID STATE" 11, no. 6s (April 7, 2023). <https://doi.org/10.52783/rj.v11i6s.1030>.

Reference: Bennison, Amira K.. *The Great Caliphs: The Golden Age of the 'abbasid Empire*. London: I.B. Tauris, 2011.

Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– Yes

Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– Yes

Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– Yes

Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– Yes

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Reference: Bennison, Amira K.. *The Great Caliphs: The Golden Age of the 'abbasid Empire*. London: I.B. Tauris, 2011.

Reference: Pormann, Peter, and Emilie Savage-Smith. *Medieval Islamic Medicine*. Edinburgh University Press, 2007. <https://doi.org/10.1515/9780748629244>.

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– Yes

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– An empire

– A state

Notes: The term "caliphate" (khilāfah) refers to a political institution which is under the leadership of an Islamic steward, the caliph. Note that some people who lived outside the ever-changing boundaries of the caliphate still considered themselves part of the umma, the Muslim community. Also note that the modern understanding of "dawlah" as a sovereign state does not fully map onto 'Abbāsīd-era understandings of the term (see Akhavi 2009 for further discussion).

Reference: Akhavi, Shahrough. "Dawlah". In *The Oxford Encyclopedia of the Islamic World*. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2009.

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– Yes

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– Yes

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the

religious group in question:

– I don't know

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– Yes

Reference: Bennison, Amira K.. *The Great Caliphs: The Golden Age of the 'abbasid Empire*. London: I.B. Tauris, 2011.

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Reference: Bennison, Amira K.. *The Great Caliphs: The Golden Age of the 'abbasid Empire*. London: I.B. Tauris, 2011.

Reference: Pormann, Peter, and Emilie Savage-Smith. *Medieval Islamic Medicine*. Edinburgh University Press, 2007. <https://doi.org/10.1515/9780748629244>.

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Yes

Notes: Beginning in the Umayyad dynasty and into the early 'Abbāsīd period, proto-schools of fiqh ("knowledge," with legal, theological, and spiritual implications, connected to the Qur'ān) developed, composed of regional circles of students who self-consciously followed a principal teacher who was an accomplished, scholarly authority in their vicinity. "Regional schools crystallized into formal legal schools (madhabs) in the late ninth to mid-tenth centuries, each having developed a set of positive legal rules and a particular jurisprudential methodology. Each regional scholar had his own approach, but all agreed broadly on the sources of law" (Rabb 2009). The Bayt al-Ḥikmah (House of Wisdom) was founded in 830 CE, during the reign of 'Abbāsīd caliph al-Ma'mūn (r. 813–833). As the leading library of its time, the Bayt al-Ḥikmah became a center of translation and included an academy for scholars; it was therefore a major center of learning in the Islamic world.

Reference: Bennison, Amira K.. *The Great Caliphs: The Golden Age of the 'abbasid Empire*. London: I.B. Tauris, 2011.

Reference: El-Hibri, Tayeb. *The Abbasid Caliphate: A History*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2021.

Reference: Rabb, Intisar A.. "Fiqh". In *The Oxford Encyclopedia of the Islamic World*. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2009.

Reference: Monastra, Yaḥyá, and William J. Kopycki. "Libraries". In *The Oxford Encyclopedia of the Islamic World*. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2009.

↳ Is formal education restricted to religious professionals:

– No

↳ Is such education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Yes

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Yes

Reference: Sourdel, Dominique. *Le Vizirat 'abbâside*. Damascus: Institut français de Damas, 1959.

Reference: Özdemir, Öznur. "Early Islamic Institutions: Administration and Taxation from the Caliphate to the Umayyads and Abbâsids" 4, no. 3 (November 30, 2018). <https://doi.org/10.25272/ijisef.490018>.

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– Yes

Reference: Talib, M.. "Annals of the Caliphs' Kitchens: Ibn Sayyar Al-warraq's Tenth-century Baghdadi Cookbook (english Translation with Introduction and Glossary) * by NAWAL NASRALLAH" 21, no. 2 (April 18, 2010). <https://doi.org/10.1093/jis/etq012>.

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– Yes

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– Yes

Reference: Bennison, Amira K.. *The Great Caliphs: The Golden Age of the 'abbasid Empire*. London: I.B. Tauris, 2011.

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– Yes

Reference: Bennison, Amira K.. *The Great Caliphs: The Golden Age of the 'abbasid Empire*. London: I.B. Tauris, 2011.

Reference: Özdemir, Öznur. "Early Islamic Institutions: Administration and Taxation from the Caliphate to the Umayyads and Abbāsids" 4, no. 3 (November 30, 2018). <https://doi.org/10.25272/ijisef.490018>.

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– Yes

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– Yes

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Theoretically, all offenses were to be tried by the qāḍī, the sharī'ah judge. But Farhat J. Ziadeh argues that the qāḍī must have lost criminal jurisdiction very early in the Islamic centuries including but not limited to the fact that rulers of Islamic empires and states, like the 'Abbāsids, "could not leave

matters of crime affecting state security in the hands of religious authorities who were loyal to a body of laws over which the state had no control... As a result the shurṭah (police) assumed the duty of investigating, prosecuting, and sentencing for most crimes with no distinction between one function and the other. The muḥtasib (inspector of the marketplace) punished those trade infractions and offenses against morals that were apparent and did not require testimony before a qāḍī's court. In addition, beginning in the early years of the 'Abbāsīd regime in the latter part of the eighth century, a new jurisdiction, called maẓālim (court of grievances) headed by the ruler, vizier, or governor, undertook to repress wrongdoers whom other courts could not control and generally to restrain oppression by officials. None of these jurisdictions was limited by the sharī'ah, as the qāḍī was. They applied mainly to customary law ('urf) or what political expediency (siyāsah) required; punishments were often arbitrary and severe."

Reference: Ziadeh, Farhat J.. "Criminal Law". In *The Oxford Encyclopedia of the Islamic World*. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2009.

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– Yes

Reference: Ghassan Mahmoud Weshah. "THE RIGHTS OF PRISONERS IN THE ABBASID STATE" 11, no. 6s (April 7, 2023). <https://doi.org/10.52783/rlj.v11i6s.1030>.

Reference: Bennison, Amira K.. *The Great Caliphs: The Golden Age of the 'abbasid Empire*. London: I.B. Tauris, 2011.

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– Yes

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– Yes

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– Yes

Reference: Gordon, Matthew. "The Turkish Officers of Samarra: Revenue and the Exercise of Authority" 42, no. 4 (1999). <https://doi.org/10.1163/1568520991201713>.

Reference: Gordon, Matthew S. *The Breaking of a Thousand Swords: A History of the Turkish Military of Samarra (A.H. 200-275/815-889 C.E.)*. Albany, NY: State University of New York Press, 2001.

Reference: Kennedy, Hugh. *The Armies of the Caliphs*. Routledge, 2013. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780203458532>.

↳ Does the religious group in question have the power to conscript:

– Yes

↳ Does the religious group in question maintain a full-time military corps (e.g. Swiss Guard):

– Yes

↳ Does the religious group in question maintain a standing army:

– Yes

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Notes: Classical Arabic was used during the 'Abbāsid period, although the language was not limited to usage by Muslims. That said, Arabic held (and continues to hold) a special status as the language of the Qur'an.

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– Yes

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

Reference: Zaouli, Lilia. *Medieval Cuisine of the Islamic World*. Berkeley: University of California Press, 2007.

Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

- Gathering
- Hunting (including marine animals)
- Fishing
- Pastoralism
- Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards
- Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Please characterize the forms/levels of food production [choose all that apply]:

- Gathering
- Hunting (including marine animals)
- Fishing
- Patorialism
- Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards
- Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

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